

A New Hybrid Model for Brain Tumor Recognition in MRI Images Based on Hand-Crafted Features and Deep Learning

Yasser Nizamli^{1*}, Anton Filatov¹, Weaam Fadel², Yulia Shichkina²

¹*Department of Software Engineering and Computer Applications, Saint Petersburg Electrotechnical University, Saint Petersburg, Russian Federation*

²*Department of Computer Science, Saint Petersburg Electrotechnical University, Saint Petersburg, Russian Federation*

*yanizamli@stud.etu.ru

Abstract— Brain tumors are among the most life-threatening cancers that can affect people of any gender or age. MRI scans manually evaluated by an expert are the initial diagnostic procedure that precedes an appropriate treatment plan. However, the human factor involves the possibility of error, and the process itself can be time-consuming and resource-consuming, ultimately putting patients' lives at risk. Therefore, efforts are being made to automate the diagnostic process through computer-aided systems, of which artificial intelligence has become the basis. This paper presents a novel system for detecting brain abnormalities in MRI images that ensures high precision without compromising the simplicity of its operational structure. In the proposed model, numerical features are extracted from grayscale MRI images using the rectangular histogram of oriented gradients method. The resulting features are fed after dimensionality reduction to a specialized sequential deep network composed of 11 learnable layers. The classification accuracy of the model reached 99.51%, outperforming many analogues, making it a promising option for supporting the diagnostic decision-making process.

Keywords—deep learning, MRI, R-HOG, brain tumor

I. INTRODUCTION

The brain is the most specialized and complex organ that controls all vital processes in the human body. A wide range of diseases can affect the brain and negatively impact its functions, including various types of tumors. A brain tumor occurs when cells divide abnormally within the brain tissue and nearby areas inside the skull. Symptoms of a brain tumor may involve headache, vomiting, nausea, emotional and behavioral changes, seizures, and blurred vision [1, 2, 3]. Brain tumors appear in several types depending on the location where they began, including gliomas, meningiomas, and pituitary tumors. These three categories constitute the majority of brain tumors, and distinguishing between them is essential for choosing the optimal treatment approach [4, 5, 6]. Medical imaging techniques such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and computed tomography (CT) are used as a basis for the procedure of detecting brain tumors. A brain MRI scan is superior in terms of accuracy and ability to show contrast compared to a CT scan. To produce an MRI, radio waves and magnetic fields are applied without the need for surgical intervention. The resulting image is then subjected to expert examination for a pathological diagnosis report [3, 4, 7]. Manual diagnostics are expensive, slow and error-prone due to the need for human intervention. Therefore, automated computer systems are usually used to support and speed up the decision-making process and reduce human error.

In order to distinguish brain tumors in MRI scans, the scientific community has presented a large number of systems that rely on different machine learning and deep learning techniques. Researchers in [4] presented a CNN model consisting of three convolutional blocks that extract features and pass them to the SoftMax element for classification. The performance of the proposed network is compared with a set of methods based on hand-crafted features such as Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) and Local Binary Pattern (LBP), where the convolutional model achieved the highest accuracy of 93%. In [5], a system is proposed that extracts features using the pre-trained deep model DenseNet169 and then feeds it to three parallel classifiers to make a collective decision, which are the decision tree, Support vector machine, and XGBoost. The proposed model achieved a classification accuracy of 95.10%. Researchers in [6] developed a network composed of five convolutional blocks arranged in a sequential manner that extracts deep features from MRI images to be classified using the SVM algorithm. The proposed system outperforms several standard deep models such as VGG16 and AlexNet with an accuracy of 96% reported. In [8], MRI images are denoised using a neural autoregressive distribution estimator and numerical features are extracted using a pre-trained VGG16 model while classification is performed using a fully connected neural network achieving an accuracy of 96.01%. Researchers in [9] proposed a three-block convolutional network architecture followed by a fully connected neural classifier. The proposed model is reported to achieve high performance with an accuracy of 96%. In [10], the well-known object detection algorithm YOLO (You Only Look Once) is adapted in its eighth version (YOLOv8) to perform the task of identifying brain tumor types in augmented MRI images. Based on the presented precision and recall parameters, the F1-score can be estimated to be 92.47%. As a parallel system, the researchers in [11] presented a model consisting of three CNNs, each consisting of five convolutional blocks that extract a distinct set of features. Each set of features is passed to a classical classifier, and the final output of the model is decided based on majority voting. The researchers reported achieving a test accuracy of 95.6%. In [12], a pre-trained VGG19 model was utilized to extract features from MRI images. The extracted features are processed using L1 penalty regularization before being passed to an SVM RBF classifier. The proposed model achieved a high accuracy of 98.53%.

The architecture of the models presented for the purpose of distinguishing brain tumor types in MRI images varies greatly, where deep learning, transfer learning, ensemble learning, and statistical methods can be observed. All studies,

including this paper, share one central goal, which is to achieve the highest classification accuracy, as it is the critical factor that can make the difference between life and death. Therefore, our main contributions are as follows: 1) To present a simple approach combining hand-crafted features and a deep learning classifier for detecting major brain tumors; 2) To employ a rectangular histogram of oriented gradients method to efficiently extract numerical features from MRI images; 3) To develop a specialized deep neural network that achieves the high performance required for the task.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fig. 1 shows the workflow of the developed system for brain tumor detection. The system starts by receiving and processing MRI images and then passing them to an instance of the rectangular histogram of oriented gradients. A well-tuned R-HOG element extracts a set of effective numerical features that represent the processed images. These features are flattened and then the dimensional space is optimized using PCA to reduce computational complexity and help prevent overfitting in the chosen classifier. The final classification task is accomplished using a specialized neural network that receives the obtained features and outputs the corresponding brain tumor type. This system can be characterized as a hybrid approach, as it integrates two distinct methodologies: manual feature extraction and deep neural networks. It is important to highlight that the PCA-based feature engineering step is essential, as the proposed approach relies on traditional statistical methods for feature acquisition rather than the automated processes typically employed in convolutional neural networks (CNNs).

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the proposed approach

A. Dataset Description

Training and evaluating the presented model requires a dataset that is appropriate for the task to be solved. In this work, the Figshare brain tumor MRI dataset is used [13]. This dataset consists of 3064 T1-CE MRI scans, each of which can belong to one of three imbalanced classes organized as follows: 709 meningiomas, 1426 gliomas, and 930 pituitary tumors. Fig. 2 shows a sample of the dataset utilized. The Figshare standard dataset was collected and organized by a team of experts and specialists, making it the only reliable dataset that deals with the main types of brain tumors.

Fig. 2. Samples from the dataset: a) glioma in the axial plane; b) meningioma in the sagittal plane; c) pituitary tumor in the coronal plane

The data is originally in MATLAB format, from which we extract grayscale MRI images, normalize, and then reduce the dimensions by half from 512×512 to 256×256 to achieve computational efficiency. Fig. 3 shows the pre-processing pipeline used.

Fig. 3. Pre-processing pipeline

B. Rectangular histogram of oriented gradients (R-HOG)

To extract features from MRI images, the Rectangular Histogram of Oriented Gradients (R-HOG) algorithm is adopted in this study. R-HOG is a statistical feature descriptor used in a wide range of computer vision applications such as classification and object detection. This method is capable of efficiently extracting shape-based features from images, which may make it a suitable choice for dealing with brain MRI images in which a tumor may appear as a distinct shape from the rest of the brain tissue. The algorithm starts by calculating the magnitudes and orientations of the image based on the horizontal and vertical gradients that can be obtained by applying a Sobel filter. The image is divided into rectangular cells with specific dimensions, for each of which a histogram vector is calculated. In this vector, the gradient orientations are used to determine the specific histogram bin to which the weighted vote from the gradient magnitudes will be assigned. A number of histogram cells are combined into blocks that are subjected to normalization. Finally, the block histograms are merged into a single vector that can be passed to the next stage in the system [14, 15].

The hyperparameters of the R-HOG algorithm are tuned experimentally to obtain the best possible performance. The cell size is chosen to be 10×10 pixels, which allows for an adequate representation of the elements in the image without generating a large number of features. Each block is formed with 2×2 cells to reduce the effect of illumination changes on the obtained features. The number of bins is chosen to be 9, covering the angle range from 0 to 180 degrees, while the L2 normalization method is adopted. Fig. 4 shows the construction of HOG features for an MRI according to the above hyperparameter tuning.

Fig. 4. R-HOG features

C. Deep neural model

After obtaining the features from the MRI images, the next step is to find the appropriate method capable of mapping this numerical data to the output that matches the correct image class. In this study, a specialized deep neural network is proposed as the final classifier in the system due to its exceptional ability to learn representations and patterns in the data. Fig. 5 shows the structure of the developed network. This neural classifier consists of an input layer and another that gives an output, in between them a dropout element and 11 fully connected neural layers. The dropout layer prevents overfitting, while the chosen deep topology ensures the formation of nonlinear decision boundaries capable of separating the sample space. It is worth noting that the input consists of 100 effective features resulting from applying PCA dimension processing to reduce the overall computational complexity of the network. Table 1 shows how to adjust the hyperparameters to achieve the best performance of the neural network.

Fig. 5. Proposed neural model architecture

TABLE I. HYPERPARAMETER TUNING

Parameter	Value
Optimizer	Adam
Learning rate	0.001
Loss	Categorical cross-entropy
Epochs	300
Shuffle	True
Batch size	16

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this study, the general-purpose Python programming language is used to design and test the experiments implemented within the Google Colab cloud computing environment. To provide the possibility of modifying and improving the model, in addition to reproducing the results, the code is open source at the following link: <https://github.com/Yasser-A-Nizamli/Hybrid-model-for-brain-tumor-detection>. 80% of the data is allocated for training the proposed network while the rest is for validation.

Figures 6 and 7 show the accuracy and loss curves of the proposed neural classifier, respectively. The accuracy increases as the iterations progress, while in parallel the loss decreases until both measures reach a degree of stability. This behavior is seen as a successful tuning of the network parameters by the optimizer, i.e. the loss function reaches a minimum value and the weights are unlikely to change significantly as the optimization process continues. The

convergence of the training and validation curves is a result of the dropout layer preventing overfitting from affecting the optimization process.

Fig. 6. Accuracy versus iterations curve for the proposed neural model

Fig. 7. Loss versus iterations curve of the proposed neural model

The classification report in Table 2 shows a set of metrics used to evaluate the classification performance. The model achieved a high test accuracy of 99.51%. The F1-score values were 98.95%, 99.49% and 100% for the meningioma, glioma and pituitary tumor classes, respectively, while the average F1-score value was 99.48%. Only two samples from the meningioma class were predicted as gliomas and only one sample from the glioma class was identified as meningioma, as the confusion matrix is shown in Fig 8.

TABLE II. CLASSIFICATION REPORT OF THE DEVELOPED MODEL

Class	Precision	Recall	F1	Avg F1	ACC
Meningioma	98.30	98.60	98.95	99.48	99.51
Glioma	99.32	99.66	99.49		
Pituitary	100	100	100		

Fig. 8. Confusion matrix of the developed model

As can be observed, the neural model is used as a classifier in the presented system and to verify its effectiveness as a necessary component in the workflow, its replacement with a set of classical machine learning algorithms is considered. Seven well-known classifiers will be used to replace the neural

model, namely Linear SVM, Logistic Regression (LR), Random Forest (RF), Decision Tree (DT), Nonlinear SVM (SVM RBF), Naive Bayes (NB), and K-nearest Neighbor (KNN). Fig. 9 shows a performance comparison between the presented neural network and the used alternatives. The nonlinear SVM achieved the highest accuracy of 94.13% among the proposed alternatives while the decision tree was the least accurate, reaching only 84.67%. The deep model performed the best compared to the rest of the algorithms, making it the most suitable choice for use as a final component in the system.

Fig. 9. Performance comparison of the proposed neural network with several machine learning classifiers

Table 3 summarizes the performance of some recent models presented by researchers to improve the recognition of brain tumors in MRI images. Despite the size and complexity of the models in the literature, the system proposed in this work outperforms them in terms of accuracy.

TABLE III. PERFORMANCE COMPARISON BETWEEN THE PROPOSED SYSTEM AND MODELS PRESENTED IN RECENT WORKS

Ref.	Method	F1	ACC
[4]	Custom CNN + SoftMax	–	93
[5]	DenseNet169 + Majority voting	94	95.10
[6]	Custom CNN + SVC	96.92	96
[8]	VGG16 + SoftMax	95.68	96.01
[9]	Custom CNN + SoftMax	95.33	96
[10]	YOLOv8 + SoftMax	92.47	–
[11]	Custom parallel CNN + Majority voting	95.07	95.6
[12]	VGG19 + Feature selection + SVC	98.34	98.53
Our	R-HOG + PCA + Custom DNN	99.48	99.51

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a hybrid machine learning approach is proposed to improve the automation of brain tumor recognition in MRI images. The presented model relies on integrating handcrafted feature extraction with deep learning methods to achieve the required high performance. The system

begins by using the Rectangular Histogram of Oriented Gradients (R-HOG) algorithm to extract features from 2D MRI images. The resulting features are processed using PCA and then fed into a deep neural model designed to map the input to the appropriate class label. The calculated performance metrics showed high effectiveness of the system compared to many counterparts in the current literature. With the expansion of MRI image categories to include more comprehensive disease conditions and the implementation of clinical testing, the developed system can be proposed as a support element for practitioners to accelerate and increase the reliability of the diagnostic decision-making process.

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